

References

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Synthesis of 2-Cyano-3-(2'-furyl)acrylamides as Potential Herbicides

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Compounds possessing amide linkage unsaturation and substituted aromatic heterocyclic systems are effective as herbicides. In continuation of our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of potential herbicides, a number of structures carrying such moieties have been synthesised and tested against two different weeds.

2-Cyano-3-(2'-furyl)acrylic acid (1) was prepared by reacting cyanoacetic acid with furfural in the presence of ammonium acetate. The acid was further treated with different amines, viz. cyclohexylamine, morpholine, 4-aminophenazone, ethylamine, n-butylamine, n-hexylamine, in presence of phosphorus oxychloride and triethylamine to get the corresponding amides (2-7). The structural assignments of the compounds were based on their ir, nmr and mass spectral data².

Compounds 1-7 were evaluated for their herbicidal activity³ against two weeds, viz., *Trianthema portulacastrum* and *Echinochloa crusgalli* at different concentrations (0, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 ppm). Most of the compounds showed little activity against *E. crusgalli* but all the compounds showed maximum activity against *T. portulacastrum*. By considering the relative activity of compounds 1-7, the herbicidal activity decreased in the order: 5 > 6 > 7 > 1 > 4 > 2 > 3. The activity of compound 5 was highest as it completely inhibited the germination, root length and shoot length of *Trianthema* sp.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 800 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a EM/390 (90 MHz) spectro-

